

PROCESSES OF DEVELOPMENT OF FINE ARTS TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract. This article covers the content of fine arts terminology, its significance and place in art studies. Visual art terms serve to correctly interpret the form, content, style, technique, and composition of works. The development of terminology and its role in art education, as well as the need to enrich the system of local terms in Uzbek art studies, are particularly emphasized. This article serves as a useful guide for art critics, students, and those interested in art.

Keywords: Fine arts, terminology, composition, color, perspective, form, texture, silhouette, art studies, aesthetic thinking, painting, contemporary art, digital art, art education, visual means of expression.

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается содержание терминологии изобразительного искусства, ее значение и место в искусствоведении. Термины изобразительного искусства служат для правильной интерпретации формы, содержания, стиля, техники и композиции произведений. Особо подчеркивается развитие терминологии и ее роль в художественном образовании, а также необходимость обогащения системы местных терминов в узбекском искусствоведении. Эта статья служит полезным руководством для искусствоведов, студентов и тех, кто интересуется искусством.

Ключевые слова: Изобразительное искусство, терминология, композиция, колорит, перспектива, форма, фактура, силуэт, искусствоведение, эстетическое мышление, живопись, современное искусство, цифровое искусство, художественное образование, средства визуального выражения.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada tasviriy san'at terminologiyasining mazmuni, uning ahamiyati va san'atshunoslikdagi o'rni yoritilgan. Tasviriy san'at atamalari asarlarning shakli, mazmuni, uslubi, texnikasi va kompozitsiyasini to'g'ri talqin qilishga xizmat qiladi. Terminologiyaning rivojlanishi va san'at ta'limidagi o'rni, shuningdek, o'zbek san'atshunosligida mahalliy terminlar tizimini boyitish zarurati alohida ta'kidlangan. Ushbu maqola san'atshunoslar, talabalar va san'atga qiziquvchilar uchun foydali qo'llanma vazifasini bajaradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tasviriy san'at, terminologiya, kompozitsiya, kolorit, perspektiva, forma, faktura, siluet, san'atshunoslik, estetik tafakkur, rassomchilik, zamonaviy san'at, raqamli san'at, san'at ta'limi, vizual ifoda vositalari.

Fine arts play an important role in reflecting human thought, aesthetic worldview, and inner psyche. This type of art has its own means of expression, styles, and genres, and special terms are used for their correct understanding, interpretation, and analysis. The terminology of fine arts is a set of terms, concepts, and expressions used in this field. These terms are widely used in art history, painting, applied arts, sculpture, graphic arts, design, and other fields.

Through terminology, it is easier to explain and analyze such important aspects of a work of art as content, form, technique, genre, style, composition, color. For example, composition refers to the arrangement and interrelationship of forms and images in a work. Color, on the other hand, represents the harmony of colors and their psychological and emotional impact. Perspective - a method of reflecting depth, distance, and proportions in the depiction of space. Such terms help to establish effective communication between the artist and the viewer.

There are many other important terms in visual arts. A color scheme is a set of colors used in a work that plays a major role in creating mood. Texture refers to whether the surface is smooth or rough.¹ Terms such as silhouette, contour, detail, form, plasticity, dynamics are also used to illuminate the technical and semantic aspects of a work of art.

The formation and development of fine art terminology is closely related to culture, history, technology, and science. New concepts arise in each epoch. For example, with the development of digital art, new terms such as pixel, vector, and graphical interface are emerging. This expands the language of modern fine art. In-depth study of terminology in art education is of great importance for students. This serves them not only in the development of theoretical knowledge, but also in the development of skills in analyzing, creating, and evaluating works. In Uzbek art history, the system of terms is also gradually enriched. Therefore, one of the important tasks is the creation of the foundations of Uzbek scientific terminology, their correct translation and implementation in practice.

¹ Суперанская А.В. "Общая терминология". – М.: LIBROKOM, 2012. – 248 с.

In conclusion, the terminology of fine art is the “language” of the world of art and is an important tool for understanding its essence, scientific analysis, and evaluation. Every artist, art historian, or art enthusiast can discover the true beauty of works of art by deeply studying these terms.

The term art history is quite complex in content. It is defined as “a complex of social sciences that studies the artistic culture of society as a whole, individual types of art, their relationship to reality, the laws of development, and their interrelationship with various phenomena of social life and culture.”²

As N.B.Kuldosheva noted, “comparative linguistics is a science related to the study of the universal characteristics of languages, historical linguistics is a science that studies the emergence, development, and change of languages, and it is no exaggeration to say that comparative terminology is one of the new directions in linguistics.” As a result of the reforms being carried out in our country, significant achievements have been made in comparative linguistics in the field of interpreting terminology as an independent field, testing the usage of terms, their practical significance, and their integration into the language. As a result, the priority of research based on practical-terminological analysis, reflecting the possibility of purposeful use of linguistic means in each area, showing the individuality of word usage, has begun to be observed.³ In our linguistics, we can see that a number of scientific studies have been carried out within the framework of the comparative study of terminology. In this regard, I. Ismailov's monograph published in 1966 is considered one of the important works. Importantly, this work thoroughly analyzes the emergence and practical application of kinship terms in Uzbek and Uyghur languages. E.M.Yusufaliev's scientific work "Linguistic Study of Pedagogical Terms Related to Education and Upbringing (Based on the Materials of the German and Uzbek Languages) " compares pedagogical terms in German and Uzbek. The issue of the presentation of fine art terms in different languages in Uzbek linguistics is highlighted in the monograph by Kh.B. Kadyrova “Terms and Explanations (the issue of Uzbek-Russian-English interpretation of national fine and applied art terms).”

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² R.A.Xojiakbarova “San’atshunoslik atamalarini o’rganish va lingvistik tavsiflashning nazariy asoslari”. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE. 2023 Boston, USA

³ Sh.Y.Usmonova “terminlarning kategorial belgi xususiyatlari”. Ta’lim va innovatsion tadqiqotlar jurnali. 2024/2. 76-80c.

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